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How to integrate Sustainability and Entrepreneurship in the Ba/Ma-Curricula?

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ABSTRACT

The paper presents the design-process of new bachelor/master-curricula at the Technische Universität Berlin. Examples for the successful integration of sustainability and entrepreneurship in the curricula are presented. The master program “innovation management, entrepreneurship and sustainability” and the one year orientation study program “MINTgrün” were introduced in detail. With the instruments of our quality-management-system the behaviour as well as the competencies of our graduates has been assessed. The centre of entrepreneurship gives support for the start-up foundation and helps in the cultural change on the way to an entrepreneurial university.

Conference Key Areas: Curriculum Development, Attractiveness of Engineering Education, Sustainability and Engineering Education

Keywords: Entrepreneurship, Sustainability, Curriculum Design, Quality Management

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INTRODUCTION

The Technische Universität Berlin (TUB) offers 51 bachelor (Ba) and 73 master (Ma) study programs. 65 % of the fields of study of TUB are in engineering, 15 % in mathematics and natural sciences and 20 % in social sciences and humanities. Sustainability and Entrepreneurship are addressed in the mission statement of TUB. Both topics should be integrated in research and education as well. In the following we will show, how sustainability and entrepreneurship are integrated in our curricula. With the instruments of our quality-management-system (QMS) we have assessed, if students and graduates have been educated in the line of our mission statement.

1 DESIGN OF A NEW CURRICULUM

1.1 General design

The flexibility in the design of the curricula has been made possible by the Bologna-process. This process has led to the transformation of the one-cycle diploma curricula through the two-cycle Ba/Ma-system. The Bologna transformation of the curricula started at TUB in the year 2004/2005. Of specific significance was the paradigm change in the design-process, the so called shift from teaching to learning. Here, the workload as well as the competencies achieved by the students during the learning process has been taken into account in the design-process for a new Ba/Ma-curriculum. In the following, we describe the design-process and the structure of a Ba/Ma-curriculum at the TUB.

Altogether, the length of study of a consecutive Ba-/Ma-program does not exceed 5 years due to German law regulations. Thus, usually mainly three-year bachelor and two-year master are realized at TUB. Each year of study is organized in two semesters. A student should get 30 credit points in one semester according to the European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System (ECTS). The credit points are corresponding to the workload of the students. One credit point is equivalent to 30 hours of work. The resulting annual workload is 1,800 hours. If the students have finished the master they have achieved 300 credit points in the consecutive bachelor-master program. *Fig. 1* shows the schematic structure of a consecutive Ba/Ma-curriculum in engineering.

Fig. 1. Schematic Ba/Ma- curriculum in engineering at TUB.

The fundamentals (like mathematics, physics, mechanics and thermodynamics) dominate in the first semesters of the bachelor in engineering. Usually, they are compulsory. The new developed curricula of the bachelor programs include project

work in the first semester courses on subjects of particular significance in the specific engineering discipline to increase the academic success. The curricula are constructed with modules. The workload of the modules is usually 6, 9 or 12 credit points. The compulsory part of the specific engineering discipline increases during the bachelor-semester. An individual profiling of the students competencies is possible with the elective-compulsory part of the discipline and the free elective part of the curriculum. Both bachelor and master programs usually contain internships in industry (range between 6 and 12 credit points). They are part of the compulsory part of the specific engineering discipline. In the master programs the fundamental part is much smaller compared to the bachelor. The curriculum is dominated by the specific compulsory and the compulsory elective part. In the last semester the master thesis is elaborated. The formal design process of a curriculum is fixed in our QMS. However, the relevant content as well as the final curriculum is established in the faculty.

1.2 Entrepreneurial modules

Around 50% of the curricula of all Master degree programs require entrepreneurship courses as mandatory or semi-mandatory, for all other students these courses are elective. The courses are organized from offering basic knowledge and first contacts to entrepreneurs up to the development of business plans and proto-types. In detail, three of these modules are described in the following:

Module venture campus (12 credit points): The strategic aim of this course is sustainable support and economic exploitation of high- tech foundation potential of the students of the TUB. As a practically oriented course, venture campus is providing its students with all business and management skills required for the establishment of a start-up company. Within this course its participants are working closely together in interdisciplinary teams preparing business plans. Although the economic realization of the business plans of the participating teams is not required in reality it is highly acknowledged and around 30 start-ups were established out of this course in the last 10 years.

Module entrepreneurship research (6 credit points): In contrast to venture campus the entrepreneurship research course is theoretically oriented as it aims at giving students a state-of-the-art overview of all streams of research around the theme entrepreneurship. The course intends to shed light on different aspects from managing and aligning internal and external networks, all facets around founding enterprises, how to explore and develop markets, how to get and exploit creative ideas, the debate effectuation und causation, just to mention a few. The course studies both theoretical models and their empirical application, changing between micro and macro-economic perspectives with a strong methodological focus. This course may also be combined with venture campus resulting in a total of 18 credit points.

Module innovation management and entrepreneurship (6 credit points): This module is an integrative course on the basics of entrepreneurship and innovation management. The course focuses on the in-depth understanding of aspects as idea generation, technology-based entrepreneurship, marketing and markets, organization and project management, new product and process development, entrepreneurial finance and human resource development. The basic course is based on introductory lectures into the above mentioned topics. In addition, the students get lectures/presentations from entrepreneurs and visit entrepreneurial venues, companies, incubators, customers etc. In order to increase the practical relevance of the course lectures are complemented with team-work on case studies or small

entrepreneurial projects. The course is the basic course on entrepreneurship and innovation for students of European Institute of Innovation and Technology (EIT) master programs and is as all other courses above taught in English.

1.3 Sustainability modules

The number of modules with sustainability contents is significantly higher than those of the entrepreneurial modules. At least 30 modules with sustainability contents are identified so far. It is the plan for this year, to realize a sustainability certificate. This certificate will be given to Ba/Ma-students, which receive at least 18 credit points from modules with sustainability content.

“tu project” supports undergraduate students with a two-years funding for an own research project. These projects have been invented in the year 2012 and they are founded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research [1]. According to the mission statement of the TUB the funded project should have a focus on sustainability and interdisciplinary teamwork. In order to start a tu project, two students have to write a project plan for a research topic. The project should run for two years and usually 15-20 students as participants should be involved. Usually, the student team is mixed in age and disciplines. According the specific workload, the participants receive credit points directly corresponding to their personal workload within the project. Up to now 34 tu projects have been realized. Topics range from “simulation game for technical environment protection” to “welfare accounting” and promise to yield new insights for the involved disciplines.

In the module “prototyping eco-innovation” aspects of sustainability and entrepreneurship have been combined.

2 EXAMPLES FOR NEW CURRICULA

2.1 Master innovation management, entrepreneurship and sustainability

Moreover, one master degree program (MSc) is specifically devoted to innovation management and entrepreneurship and is the most attractive one in Germany with more than 500 applicants for 35 places. It is the dual degree master’s program “innovation management and entrepreneurship” (IME) organized in cooperation with the University of Twente, the Warsaw School of Economics, the Higher School of Economics in Moscow, the St. Petersburg Polytechnical University and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology. Students are supposed to stay two semesters in Berlin and two semesters in one of the partner institutions. The compulsory area comprises 30 credit points. Modules are “entrepreneurship research”, “venture campus”, “innovation economics” and “strategic management”. In the compulsory elective part the students should select modules with a total of 30 credit points. 30 credit points are elective. It is strongly recommended, to elect courses in the fields of management, innovation management, entrepreneurship, business administration, economics and industrial engineering and management. The master’s thesis is usually completed in the fourth semester. It comprises 30 credit points. The last ranking 2015 based on the evaluation of human resource departments made by “Wirtschaftswoche” sees the entrepreneurship education at TUB among the top ranked business education in Germany. The eduniversal ranking 2015/16 ranked this master as the best in Germany and the number 42 worldwide. In the CHE Master Ranking 2014, the IME master is classified as Germany’s leading master program in 5 out of 14 categories. The IME is leading in “Study comfort”, “Practice focus”, Scientific focus”, “Support in international exchange” and in International orientation”. Recently, the curriculum was redesigned and a new

sustainability track has been opened. In the winterterm 2017/2018 the new master “innovation management, entrepreneurship and sustainability” will start. The structure of entrepreneurship courses at TUB also served as blue-print for the educational programs at the EIT and was copied in many European universities.

2.2 Orientation study program MINTgrün

MINTgrün (English STEMgreen) is a one year orientation study program. It addresses high school graduates who are interested in natural sciences and engineering but don't yet know what exactly to study. The superscript “grün” indicates the conceptual focus on ecological und social questions. The target of MINTgrün is to show them the several possibilities of a future in natural sciences, technology, engineering and mathematics. A special target group are young women, who miss aspects of sustainability in the regular engineering curricula. Mandatory courses are the “science window” and the “orientation course” as well as the “MINTgrün laboratories” (all 6 credit points). In the laboratories, real project work has to be done. Examples of the labs already have been published [2, 3]. In the mandatory elective part (42 credit points), the students can choose all modules within the university. Popular are modules like mathematics, physics and computer science (6 credit points). All received credit points are usually accepted if the students will change to another bachelor-degree program. MINTgrün started in 2012 with 77 students. The number of participants increases continuously up to 490 in the year 2016. Today, we have 38 % female students (average at TUB in engineering is 28 %, overall 33 %). The program enables approximately 82 % of the MINTgrün students to make an informed decision on their later field of study, 74 % of them stay in the field of STEM. 10 % see their future outside academic contexts. In the next 4 years we will investigate, if the success rate of former MINTgrün students is higher from those students, who choose their bachelor directly.

2.3 Master programs at the TUB- EUREF campus

At the TUB-European Energy Forum (EUREF) campus, three international MBA-degree-programs where actually offered since the year 2016: “energy management”, “european and international energy law” and “building sustainability – management methods for energy efficiency”. The new program “sustainability mobility management” will start in the winterterm 17/18. The energy transition of the society is in the focus in these master degree programs. The study location is on the site of the EUREF around the historical Gasometer in Berlin-Schöneberg. The campus is the setting of an innovative community including applied research, economic and policy consultancies mainly based on the philosophy of sustainability.

3 QUALITY MANAGEMENT

3.1 Process Management

The QMS of the TUB is designed close to the ISO-9001 norm. The relevant processes are available on the website of TUB. In order to evaluate the performance in teaching and learning several instruments are used in our QMS. However, there often is no simple way from check to act, but the results are helpful both for the internal discussion and marketing purposes.

3.2 Graduate studies and impact for the region

Continuous improvement of the curricula was performed by using the results of the quality management instruments. Especially our graduate surveys, which were performed in cooperation with Incher Kassel since 2009 in a nation-wide-project are very well accepted inside the university. The graduates of every year were polled

with a detailed questionnaire 1.5 year after graduation. The response rate is usually around 35 % and the results are representative. Current investigations concern the TUB-graduates of the year 2014. Table 1 present some keyfacts for this graduation year.

Table 1: Keyfacts of the graduation survey for the TUB-graduates of the year 2014.

Keyfacts of the graduation cohort 2014	Bachelor degree	Master degree	Diplom degree	TUB overall average
Percentage of female gender	28	30	30	30
Average age at time of graduation (years)	25.3	28.1	30.4	27.4
Average grade at graduation	2.2	1.7	1.8	1.9
Average duration of study (Fachsemester, Median)	8.0	5.0	14.0	8.0
Average duration for job search (in months; Median)	2	3	4	3
Average income (pre-tax) per month in € (Median; Only full-time employees)	2,626	3,251	3,251	3,251
Overall satisfaction with TUB (Median 1=very satisfied / 5=very unsatisfied)	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Overall job satisfaction (Median 1=very satisfied / 5=very unsatisfied)	2.0	2.0	2.0	2.0
Number of graduates (N)	525	448	200	1173

Both the overall satisfaction with the TUB, as well as job satisfaction at the first job is evaluated good (= 2.0) by bachelor and master graduates. However, the average salary per month in the first year is significantly lower for the bachelor graduates (€ 2,626) compared to the master graduates (€ 3,251). To explain the difference we like to remark that Ba-programs are viewed in the German public sector as leading to second-rank careers ("gehobener Dienst"), whereas Ma-programs lead to first-rank careers ("höherer Dienst"). In the last three graduation cohorts, the salary of the bachelor graduates has increased about € 750 whereas the Ma-value remains constant. This indicates the raising acceptance of bachelor graduates on the job market. In the last four graduation cohorts, the graduates received their first jobs outside university one to three months after graduation. Graduate studies also show the relevance of the graduates for the regional job market. These results are of great importance for the society and the regional government as well. *Fig. 2* shows, that more than 60 % of the TUB-graduates (graduation years 2011, 2012, 2013, 2014 and 2015) find their first job in Berlin. In computer science, nearly 80 %, except in 2015, remain to work in Berlin.

Berlin has become the first start-up city in Germany. 17 % of the German start-ups had their headquarters in Berlin in 2016. Berlin has also the highest foundation rate for start-ups in computer science. In order to strengthen the science in this area, a new centre (Einstein Centre for Digital Future) as a joint venture between Berlin universities and industry with the financial support of the government and the Einstein-foundation has been opened at the 3th of April 2017 in Berlin. Here, up to 50 new professors in the field of computer science come to the universities and will increase the power of the in this area significantly. The overall funding is € 38.8 million for the next six years.

Fig. 2: Berlin as a working place for TUB graduates.

Another fact is remarkable in our graduate studies: 44 % of our graduates could imagine, that they will found their own company in the future. In computer science, the corresponding amount of 61 % is significantly higher. The detailed result for the different disciplines is shown in figure 3.

Fig. 3: Inclination to entrepreneurship of TUB-graduates (Graduation year 2013).

Recently, a new study shows the courses offered for the EIT effect entrepreneurial intentions and attitudes significantly positive in only five weeks [4]. It has been proved, that opinion leadership in entrepreneurial related topics positively influences changes in the pro-entrepreneurial intentions. Therefore, we address some of these topics (i. e. start-up science slam, talks by famous founders...) even in the opening ceremony for the new freshman students since 2015. However, we do not have panel studies or tracking which proves the careers of our graduates so far.

4 THE CENTRE FOR ENTREPRENEURSHIP

The TUB aims at profoundly embedding the subject of entrepreneurship in all areas of the university and to make use of the huge potential of commercializing inventions and research results. It's not surprising that the university decided to do the next step and to concentrate its competencies in research, education and practical entrepreneurship support within the Centre for Entrepreneurship (CfE) which was established in April 2010. The advantage of this new integrated institution is its long-term orientation. Thus, the CfE is financed not only by third-party funding but has also stable financing from university-side. Before designing the TUB CfE programmed, its staff benchmarked successful counterparts at Stanford, the Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Danish Technical University and ETH Zurich. The activities of the CfE are organizationally divided into three main areas: research, education and practice (advice and support). Thereby, the research activities are located at the Chair of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management. The Founder's Service is responsible for the practical entrepreneurship support of TUB entrepreneurs. The education activities, finally, are coordinated and executed by both the Chair of Entrepreneurship and Innovation Management and the Founder's Service and where described above. The success of the CfE has been measured recently. There are 25 high-tech start-ups per annum in average. More than 70 % of those who have received intensive coaching since 2007 are still in business. The CfE has a great economic impact for the city and beyond: In 2015, 758 spin-off companies run by Alumni of TUB employed up to 20.000 people. The overall turnover was 2.7 billion Euros. Some of the start-ups have direct connection to sustainability topics. On example is the start-up akvola which was founded in 2013. The idea is to make a sustainable sea water treatment. The company receive the ACES Green award and is described in [5]. The "Gründungsradar" an evaluation of academic entrepreneurship sees the TUB on position three out of all larger German universities.

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